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DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONCEPT OF URBANIZATION OF BUKHARA REGION

Mirzaev Shamsiddin

Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology. Associate Professor Scientific Leader

Akramov Doniyor Rustam ugli

Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology, master's degree in building and construction architecture

Annotation: The concept of urbanization of Bukhara region has evolved over time in response to various economic, social, and political factors. Historically, Bukhara has been an important center of trade and commerce, with the ancient Silk Road connecting China and Europe passing through the region. This led to the growth of urban centers in the region, including Bukhara city, which became a major center for Islamic scholarship, culture, and arts.

Keywords: The concept , city, town, urban settlement, urbanization, level of urbanization, urbanization process

BUXORO VILOYAT HUDUDINING URBANIZATSIYA KONTSEPTSIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQISH

Mirzaev Shamsiddin

Buxoro muhandislik va texnologiya instituti. Dotsent Ilmiy Raxbar

Akramov Doniyor Rustam o‘g‘li

Buxoro muhandislik va texnologiya instituti Bino va inshootlar arxitekturasi mutaxassisligi magistranti

Buxoro viloyatining urbanizatsiya kontseptsiyasi vaqt o‘tishi bilan turli iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va siyosiy omillar ta‘sirida rivojlanib bordi. Tarixan Buxoro muhim savdo va savdo markazi bo‘lib, Xitoy va Yevropani bog‘lovchi qadimiy Ipak yo‘li mintaqadan o‘tgan. Bu mintaqada shahar markazlarining, jumladan, Buxoro shahrining o‘sishiga olib keldi, bu esa islom ilmi, madaniyati va san‘atining yirik markaziga aylandi.

Kalit so‘zlar: kontseptsiya, shahar, shaharcha, shahar manzilgohi, urbanizatsiya, urbanizatsiya darajasi, urbanizatsiya jarayoni

The concept of urbanization of Bukhara region has evolved over time in response to various economic, social, and political factors. Historically, Bukhara has been an important center of trade and commerce, with the ancient Silk Road connecting China and Europe passing through the region. This led to the growth of urban centers in the region, including Bukhara city, which became a major center for Islamic scholarship, culture, and arts.

Fig 1

Population

The Population of Bukhara in 2013 was 369,044, increasing at an average annual rate of 7.5% since 2000. The population of Bukhara in 2000 was 138,578, increasing at an average annual rate of 12.8% since 1991, when its population was 42,305.

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China and Europe passing through the region. This led to the growth of urban centers in the region, including Bukhara city, which became a major center for Islamic scholarship, culture, and arts.

Urban Extent

The Urban Extent of Bukhara in 2013 was 21,636 hectares, increasing at an average annual rate of 7.6% since 2000. The urban extent in 2000 was 7,983 hectares, increasing at an average annual rate of 17.4% since 1991, when its urban extent was 1,596 hectares.

1991 2000 2013

Urban Extent

- Urban Built-up
- Suburban Built-up
- Rural Built-up
- Urbanized Open Space

Exurban Area

- Exurban Built-Up Area
- Exurban Open Space

Rural Open Space

- Rural Open Space

Fig 2

Composition of Added Area

A total of 9,992 hectares of built-up area was added to the Bukhara urban extent between 2000 and 2013. Of that added built-up area, 21% was Infill, 14% was Extension, 3% was Leapfrog, and 63% was Inclusion. A total of 3,436 hectares of built-up area was added to the urban extent between 1991 and 2000. Of that added built-up area, 12% was Infill, 57% was Extension, 1% was Leapfrog, and 30% was Inclusion.

- 1991-2000 2000-2013
- Built-up Area 1991
 - Infill
 - Extension
 - Leapfrog
 - Inclusion

Share of built up area occupied by roads and boulevards

Average Street Width

Fig 3

However, the Soviet era saw significant changes in Bukhara's urbanization as the government promoted a centralized system of economic development, focusing on industrialization and urbanization. This led to the mass migration of people from rural areas to urban centers, including Bukhara city. During this period, the government constructed large housing complexes and industrial facilities in the region to support the growing population.

Since the collapse of the Soviet Union, the government has promoted a market-oriented approach to development, focusing on attracting foreign investment and promoting small and medium-sized enterprises. This approach has led to the development of tourism in the region, which has resulted in significant growth in the hospitality industry and the reconstruction of historic sites, such as the Ark citadel and Samanid mausoleum in Bukhara city.

Fig 4

Blocks and Plots

Average block size in Bukhara's 1990-2014 expansion area was 10 hectares, compared to 4 hectares in its pre-1990 area.

Pre 1990 1990 - 2014

Fig 4

The concept of urbanization of Bukhara region today involves the promotion of sustainable development, balancing economic growth with environmental protection and social development. This includes the development of modern

infrastructure, such as highways, airports, and public transportation, promoting renewable energy, and preserving the region's cultural heritage. The government is also investing in the development of education and healthcare facilities, as well as

supporting small and medium-sized enterprises in the region.

Arterial Roads

The density of arterial roads in Bukhara's 1990-2014 expansion was 0.84 km/km², compared to 1.58 km/km² in its pre-1990 area.

The share of built-up area within walking distance of an arterial road in Bukhara's 1990-2014 expansion area was 69%, compared to 89% in the pre-1990 area.

1991 2013

Overall, the concept of urbanization of Bukhara region continues to evolve, responding to the changing economic, social, and political factors, while striving to achieve sustainable development and preserve the region's unique cultural identity. The concept of urbanization of Bukhara region has evolved over time, with historic factors such as the Silk Road leading to the growth of urban centers, including Bukhara city. During the Soviet era, the government promoted a centralized system of economic development, leading to mass migration to urban centers and the construction of large housing complexes and industrial facilities. Since the collapse of the Soviet Union, the government has promoted a market-oriented approach to development, focusing on attracting foreign investment and promoting sustainable development. This approach involves the development of modern infrastructure, promoting renewable energy, and preserving the region's cultural heritage. The government is also investing in the development of education and healthcare facilities and supporting small and medium-sized enterprises. Overall, the concept of urbanization of Bukhara region involves balancing economic growth with environmental protection and social development, while preserving the region's unique cultural identity.

In recent years, there has been a shift from a centralized economic approach to a more market-oriented approach, focusing on attracting foreign

investment and promoting small and medium-sized enterprises. The development of infrastructure such as highways, airports, and public transportation has facilitated the process of urbanization, leading to renewed development of Bukhara city and other urban centers within the region.

The promotion of sustainable urbanization, which focuses on minimizing the impact of urbanization on the environment, is another vital aspect of the concept of urbanization of Bukhara. The preservation of the region's cultural heritage through the promotion of responsible tourism and the protection of historic sites is also a significant focus.

In summary, the concept of urbanization of Bukhara focuses on urban development that is environmentally sustainable, socially and culturally responsible, and in harmony with the region's unique historical and cultural heritage.

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